

Sexual and Reproductive Health Glossary

TRANSLATED INTO PASHTO

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ENGLISH MEDICAL TERM	PASHTO MEDICAL TERM	COLLOQUIAL EXPRESSIONS
<p>Abdominal ultrasound</p> <p>A type of imaging test to look at organs in the abdomen. A gel is applied to the skin over the abdomen before a handheld probe is gently pressed against the skin. The ultrasound machine sends out sound waves that reflect off body structures to create a picture.</p>	د نس التراساوند	د نس تلویزونی معاینه
<p>Abortion (termination of pregnancy)</p> <p>A method to end a pregnancy. A medication abortion uses medicines to end the pregnancy. A procedural abortion uses a medical procedure to remove the pregnancy from the uterus.</p>	د جنین سقط (د امېندواری- پای ته رسول)	
<p>Abstinence</p> <p>Not having sex.</p>	له جنسي اړیکو پرهیز یا ډډه	
<p>Amniocentesis (amniotic fluid test)</p> <p>A test done during pregnancy to diagnose certain conditions in an unborn baby. The provider will insert a thin needle into the abdomen and withdraw a small amount of amniotic fluid.</p>	امنیوسنتیزیس (د امنیوتیک د مایع معاینه)	
<p>Amniotic fluid</p> <p>The fluid that surrounds the unborn baby during pregnancy.</p>	د امنیوتیک مایع	
<p>Amniotic sac</p> <p>The fluid-filled structure inside the uterus that holds the amniotic fluid. The amniotic sac cushions and protects the developing baby</p>	د امنیوتیک کڅوړه	
<p>Anemia</p> <p>A condition in which the blood does not carry enough oxygen to the rest of the body. Anemia can make a person feel tired, weak, and/or dizzy.</p>	کم خوني	

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<p>Anus</p> <p>The end of the digestive track where stool comes out of the body.</p>	مقعد	
<p>Areola</p> <p>The darker skin around the nipple.</p>	هاله (د تي د نوک شاوخوا توروالی)	
<p>Assisted vaginal delivery</p> <p>The use of medical tools to help guide a baby's head out of the vagina.</p>	د مهبل له لارې مرستندويه زېږول	د لمن له لارې مرستندويه ولادت
<p>Auscultation</p> <p>The action of listening to the sounds of the body (heart, lungs, or other organs). Auscultation is usually done using a tool called a stethoscope.</p>	سمع (د مور په نس کی د ماشوم د زره د دربا غږاوریدل)	
<p>Autonomy</p> <p>A patient's right to make decisions about their medical care without others trying to influence their decision.</p>	خپلواکه	
<p>Barrier method</p> <p>Birth control that stops sperm from entering the vagina. Examples include: condoms, diaphragms, cervical caps, and contraceptive sponges.</p>	له امپندواره کېدو نه د مخنيوي لاره	
<p>Benign</p> <p>Not cancer.</p>	سليم	
<p>Biopsy</p> <p>The removal of cells or tissue for laboratory examination under a microscope.</p>	بيوپسي (د معاینې لپاره د وجود څخه کوچنی نمونه اخيست)	

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<p>Birth control implant (contraceptive implant)</p> <p>A small, thin, flexible, rod inserted under the skin of the upper arm. The implant releases hormones that prevent pregnancy.</p>	د امپندواری ضد ایمپلانټ (د امپندواری د مخنیوي ایمپلانټ)	
<p>Birth control injection</p> <p>A shot of medication that prevents pregnancy. Pregnancy is prevented because eggs are not released from the ovaries.</p>	د امپندواری ضد پیچکاری	
<p>Birth control patch</p> <p>A skin patch worn on the lower abdomen, buttocks, or upper body. The patch releases a medication absorbed through the skin that prevents pregnancy.</p>	د امیندواری د کنترول د پوستکی پیچ	
<p>Birth control ring</p> <p>A small flexible ring placed in the vagina. The ring releases a medication that prevents pregnancy.</p>	د امپندواری د کنترول کری	
<p>Birth plan</p> <p>A written outline of what one would like to happen to support their health and experience during labor and delivery.</p>	د زېرون پلان	
<p>Birth spacing (pregnancy spacing)</p> <p>The time from one child's birth until the next pregnancy.</p>	د امپندواری واټن	
<p>Bladder</p> <p>A hollow, muscular organ in which urine is stored.</p>	مثانه	
<p>Blood transfusion</p> <p>When blood from one person is given to another person through a tube placed in the vein. The blood is first sterilized.</p>	د وینې تزریق	

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<p>Braxton-Hicks contractions (false labor pains)</p> <p>Irregular, mildly uncomfortable contractions of the uterus that occur during pregnancy.</p>	د براكستون-هيكس انقباضات (د زېږون مصنوعي دردونه)	
<p>Breast</p> <p>Glandular organs located on the chest. Breast tissue contains the glands that make milk.</p>	تی	
<p>Breast cancer (malignancy)</p> <p>Cancer that forms in tissues of the breast.</p>	د تی سرطان (مالیګننسی)	د تی یا سینی سرطان
<p>Breast self-exam</p> <p>The process of checking one's breasts for lumps or other changes. Breast self-exams can help a person learn how their breasts normally look and feel and notice when changes occur.</p>	په خپله د تی معاینه کول	
<p>Breastfeeding</p> <p>The act of feeding breast milk to an infant. Babies can be fed directly from the breast, or breast milk can be pumped and then fed to the baby from a bottle. Milk can be pumped by hand with a manual (hand-powered) pump or with an electric pump.</p>	د مور په شېدو سره تغذیه	
<p>Breech presentation</p> <p>The baby is positioned for delivery with the buttocks or feet first rather than the head.</p>	بریچ (هغه ماشوم چې پر پښو وي)	
<p>Cervical cancer</p> <p>Cancer that forms in tissues of the cervix.</p>	د سرویکس سرطان (د رحم د عنق سرطان)	
<p>Cervix</p> <p>The opening between the vagina and the uterus.</p>	سرویکس (د رحم د عنق)	

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<p>Cesarean delivery (c-section)</p> <p>Delivery of a baby from the uterus through a cut or incision made in the abdomen.</p>	د سيزارين زېږون (سيزارين)	عمليات له لاری د ماشوم زېږون
<p>Circumcision</p> <p>The surgical removal of the foreskin that covers the head of the penis.</p>	سنت کول	
<p>Clinical breast exam</p> <p>A physical exam of the breast performed by a doctor to check for lumps or other changes.</p>	د ثديه (تي) کلينيکي معاینه	
<p>Colostrum</p> <p>The fluid that comes out of the breasts at the beginning of milk production.</p>	کلوستروم	
<p>Colposcopy</p> <p>A procedure to examine the cervix and vagina. A vinegar solution may be used to make abnormal tissue easier to see. If abnormalities are seen, a biopsy may be taken.</p>	کولپوسکوپي	د لمنی له لار معاینه
<p>Congenital</p> <p>A condition that a person has from birth.</p>	ماږزادي	
<p>Consent</p> <p>An agreement between people to engage in sexual activity.</p>	خوښه/اجازه	
<p>Constipation</p> <p>A condition, characterized by infrequent bowel movement, in which stool becomes hard, dry, and difficult to pass.</p>	قبضيت	

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<p>Contraception (birth control)</p> <p>Devices or medications used to prevent pregnancy.</p>	له امېندواری مخنیوی (د امېندواری کنټرول)	
<p>Deep vein thrombosis</p> <p>A condition in which a blood clot forms in one or more of the deep veins in the body, usually the legs.</p>	ترومبوسس (د ویني غوټه کیدل)	
<p>Diagnostic tests</p> <p>Tests that look for a disease or cause of a disease in people with symptoms.</p>	تشخیصیه معاینات	
<p>Diaphragm (cervical cap)</p> <p>A bendable cup placed inside the vagina to cover the cervix and prevent pregnancy as a barrier method of contraception.</p>	ډیافراگم (د رحم د خولې سرپون)	
<p>Dilation</p> <p>The opening of the cervix. This occurs as labor nears.</p>	ډیالیشن یا د رحم د عنق خلاصېدل	
<p>Dilation and Curettage</p> <p>A procedure to remove tissue from inside the uterus. A D&C may be used to clear the uterine lining after a miscarriage or abortion.</p>	د رحم خلاصېدل او کورتاژ	
<p>Eclampsia</p> <p>The new onset of seizures occurring in pregnancy or after pregnancy that are linked to high blood pressure. People with eclampsia may also have damage to other body organs.</p>	ایکلمپسي	
<p>Ectopic pregnancy</p> <p>A pregnancy in a place other than the uterus, usually in one of the fallopian tubes.</p>	د رحم نه بهر د حمل اخیستل	

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<p>Ejaculation</p> <p>The discharge of semen from the tip of the penis.</p>	انزال کېدل	
<p>Emergency oral contraception</p> <p>Method used to prevent pregnancy after unprotected sexual intercourse.</p>	له امېندواړه کېدو نه د بېرني مخنيوي لپاره خوراکي درمل	
<p>Endometrium</p> <p>The lining of the uterus.</p>	اندومتر	
<p>Epidural block</p> <p>A type of pain medication that is injected into the space around the spinal nerves.</p>	د بې حسي پيچکاري	
<p>Episiotomy</p> <p>A surgical cut made in the area between the vagina and the anus to widen the vaginal opening for delivery.</p>	ايبيزيتومي (د مهبل جراحي پريکول يا خېرې کول)	
<p>External Cephalic Version (ECV)</p> <p>A technique in which the doctor attempts to manually move a baby in breech position into the head-down position.</p>	د رحم خولې ته د ماشوم د سر برابرول	
<p>External condom</p> <p>A thin pouch that keeps sperm from entering the vagina. External condoms are worn on the penis. Condoms are used during sex to prevent sexually transmitted infections and pregnancy.</p>	کانډوم	
<p>Fallopian tubes</p> <p>Muscular tubes that connect the ovaries to the uterus. Fertilization of an egg usually takes place in a fallopian tube.</p>	نفرونه	

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<p>Family planning</p> <p>The information, means and methods that allow individuals and families to decide if and when to have children.</p>	د کورنۍ تنظیم	
<p>Fertility awareness (natural family planning) method</p> <p>A set of practices to track a person's natural body functioning to determine when they are most likely to get pregnant.</p>	د امیندواري او کورنۍ تنظیم په هکله معلومات	
<p>Full-term</p> <p>A baby born on time, between 39 weeks and 42 weeks.</p>	په وخت سره زېږون	
<p>Gynecologist</p> <p>A doctor who specializes in women's reproductive health.</p>	د ولادي متخصص	
<p>Hemorrhage</p> <p>Heavy bleeding.</p>	شدیده خونریزې	
<p>Hemorrhoids</p> <p>Swollen blood vessels located in or around the anus.</p>	بواسیر	
<p>Hormones</p> <p>Chemicals made in the body that control the function of cells or organs.</p>	هورمونونه	
<p>Hysterectomy</p> <p>A surgery to remove the uterus.</p>	هیستریکتومي یا د لمنې له لارې د رحم عملیات	داولاد د جای لری کول

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<p>Induction</p> <p>When a healthcare provider helps initiate or progress the childbirth process using medications or other medical techniques.</p>	د زیږون مصنوعی درد	
<p>Infertility</p> <p>When someone who wants to become pregnant does not become pregnant after having sex regularly. To be defined as infertility, you must have been trying to become pregnant for 1 year without using birth control.</p>	عقامت (بې اولادي)	
<p>Injection</p> <p>Use of a syringe and needle to push fluids or drugs into the body.</p>	پیچکاری	
<p>Internal condom</p> <p>A thin pouch that keeps sperm from entering the vagina. Internal condoms are inserted into the vagina. Condoms are used during sex to prevent sexually transmitted infections and pregnancy.</p>	شخینه کاندوم	
<p>Intimate partner violence</p> <p>The use of physical, sexual, or emotional threats or actions against a romantic partner. This includes non-consensual sex, being hit or kicked, and more.</p>	د زوند د شریک له خوا تاوتریخوالی	
<p>Intrauterine device (IUD)</p> <p>A small device that is inserted and left inside the uterus to prevent pregnancy. Depending on the type of IUD, it can remain in place for 3, 5, or 10 years.</p>	ای-یو-دی (د ولادت د مخنیوي له پاره د رحم دننه وسیله)	لوپ
<p>Labor</p> <p>The tightening of the uterine muscles that cause the cervix to open, thin, and stretch. Labor allows for the baby to be born.</p>	د زیږون درد	

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<p>Lactation</p> <p>The production of breast milk.</p>	شېدې ورکول	
<p>Lactational Amenorrhea Method (LAM)</p> <p>A temporary method of birth control that is based on the natural way the body prevents the release of an egg when a person is exclusively breastfeeding. LAM is typically effective for up to 6 months postpartum if the menstrual period has not returned.</p>	ماشوم ته د شیدو ورکلو له لارې له بیا امیندواره کیدو نه مخنیوی کول	
<p>Long-acting hormonal method</p> <p>Birth control that last years after insertion or until the device is removed. Examples include: intrauterine devices or birth control implants.</p>	اوږد مهاله هورموني میتود	د اوږدمهاله هورموني درملو په استعمال له امیندواري نه مخنوي
<p>Mammogram</p> <p>An x-ray, a type of imaging test that takes pictures of bones and soft tissues of the breast to look for early signs of breast cancer.</p>	ماموگرام (د اکسری ماشین په استعمال د تی یا سینو معاینه)	
<p>Mastectomy</p> <p>Surgery to remove part or all of the breast as a way to treat or prevent breast cancer.</p>	ماستکتومي (د تی پریکول)	
<p>Mastitis</p> <p>An inflammation of the breast tissue, sometimes due to an infection. Mastitis is most common during breastfeeding.</p>	د ثدی یا تی التهاب	گزک
<p>Menopause</p> <p>The time when a person's menstrual periods stop permanently. Menopause is confirmed 12 months after their last period.</p>	د میاشتنۍ ناروغۍ دریدل	

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<p>Menstruation (period)</p> <p>The regularly monthly shedding of blood and tissue from the uterus that happens when a person is not pregnant.</p>	مياشتنۍ ناروغۍ (حيض)	
<p>Miscarriage (spontaneous abortion)</p> <p>The unexpected or spontaneous loss of a uterine pregnancy before 20 weeks.</p>	د اميندواری په خپل سر ضايع کيدل (بنفسهي سقط)	نقصان
<p>Nausea and vomiting in pregnancy (morning sickness)</p> <p>Feel like throwing up, and throwing up, that occurs during early pregnancy.</p>	د اميندواری په مهال د زړه بدوالی او استفراغ (سهارنۍ ناروغۍ)	د زړه بدوالی او کی / استفراغ
<p>Neonatologist</p> <p>A doctor who specializes in the care of premature babies or newborns with complex health conditions.</p>	نيوناتولوجيست يا د نويو زېږول شوو ماشومانو متخصص	
<p>Obstetrician</p> <p>A doctor who provides care during pregnancy and delivers babies.</p>	د نسايي متخصص	
<p>Oral contraception</p> <p>Medications, specifically pills, used to prevent pregnancy or to decrease monthly bleeding and pain caused by the menstrual cycle.</p>	د درملو په خوړلو سره له اميندواره کېدو نه مخنيوی	
<p>Osteoporosis</p> <p>A condition in which bones thin and become weak, allowing them to break more easily.</p>	استيوپوروسيس (د هډوکو ضعیفه کيدل)	
<p>Ovarian cancer</p> <p>Cancer that forms in tissues of the ovary.</p>	د تخمدان سرطان	

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<p>Ovarian cyst</p> <p>Sacs, usually filled with fluid, in or on the surface of an ovary. Most ovarian cysts are harmless and will go away on their own. Sometimes ovarian cysts can become twisted or rupture requiring immediate surgical removal.</p>	د تخمدان کېست	
<p>Pap smear (Papanicolaou test)</p> <p>A procedure to test for cervical cancer or cell changes that may lead to cervical cancer. A tool called a speculum is used to look inside the vagina and a small brush is used to gently remove cells from the surface of the cervix and the area around it so they can be checked.</p>	پاپ سمیر (د پاپانیکولا معاینه)	
<p>Pediatrician</p> <p>A doctor who cares for infants, children, and young adults.</p>	د ماشومانو متخصص	
<p>Pelvic exam</p> <p>An internal and external physical exam of the pelvic organs including the vagina, cervix, uterus, fallopian tubes, and ovaries.</p>	د لگن خاصرې معاینه	
<p>Perinatal</p> <p>The time before and immediately after birth. Typically lasts from 20-22 weeks gestation and 1-4 weeks after birth.</p>	له زېږون وړاندې او وروسته وخت	
<p>Perineal tear</p> <p>An injury to the tissue between the vagina and the anus. A perineal tear can happen during a vaginal delivery and will be repaired by a doctor.</p>	د مقعد پر لورې د مهبل څېرې کېدل	
<p>Perineum</p> <p>The area between the vagina and the anus.</p>	پرینه	

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<p>Placenta</p> <p>An organ that develops in the uterus during pregnancy and provides nutrients and oxygen to the developing baby. The placenta also removes waste from the baby's blood.</p>	پلاستیا	ملگري/پلاستیا
<p>Polycystic Ovary Syndrome (PCOS)</p> <p>A very common condition caused by an imbalance of reproductive hormones. This imbalance can lead to cysts on the ovaries, menstrual problems, and difficulty becoming pregnant. PCOS is a treatable condition.</p>	د پولي کيسټيک تخمدان سنډروم	د تخمدانونو کيسټونه /په تخمدانونو کې د ابو کڅوړي پيداکيدل
<p>Post-term</p> <p>A baby is born late, after 42 weeks.</p>	له وخت نه تير زېږون	
<p>Postpartum</p> <p>The weeks following the birth of a child.</p>	له زېږون وروسته	لنگه بنځه/زچه بنځه
<p>Postpartum depression</p> <p>A type of depression that develops in the first year after the birth of a child. People with postpartum depression experience emotional high and lows, frequent crying, anxiety, and may have trouble caring for their baby. Postpartum depression is common and can be treated. Please talk to a health care professional.</p>	له زېږون وروسته ډيپريشن (ژور خپگان)	
<p>Pre-eclampsia</p> <p>A condition that occurs when a pregnant person has a high blood pressure. The high blood pressure can damage other parts of their body.</p>	پري-ايکلامپسي	
<p>Pre-term</p> <p>A baby is born early, before 37 weeks of pregnancy.</p>	له وخت نه مخکې زېږون	

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<p>Pregnancy</p> <p>The state of carrying a developing baby within the uterus. Pregnancy usually lasts about 40 weeks.</p>	امپندواري	
<p>Prenatal care</p> <p>The prenatal period is the time during pregnancy and before birth. Prenatal care is the health care received by a pregnant person before they give birth.</p>	د امپندواري پر مهال روغتيايي خدمات	
<p>Prenatal vitamins</p> <p>Medication made for pregnant people that contain the vitamins and minerals needed during, before, and after pregnancy.</p>	د امپندواري پر مهال وېټامينونه	
<p>Primary care provider (PCP)</p> <p>A doctor or other licensed medical professional who manages a person's health care over time, most commonly in a clinic setting.</p>	د لومړنيو خدماتو وړاندې کوونکی (PCP)	
<p>Quickening</p> <p>When a pregnant person first feels their baby move in their uterus.</p>	په رحم کې د ماشوم ښوریدل	
<p>Screening tests</p> <p>Tests that look for possible signs of disease in people who do not have symptoms.</p>	د سکرینینګ معاینات	
<p>Sexual agency</p> <p>The ability to identify, communicate, and negotiate one's sexual needs.</p>	جنسي اختیار/واک	
<p>Sexual violence</p> <p>Sex acts or attempts that are forced on one person by another.</p>	جنسي زورزیاتې	

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<p>Sexually transmitted infections (STIs)</p> <p>An infection that is spread by sexual contact.</p>	جنسي ساري عفونتونه/ مکروبونه	
<p>Short-acting hormonal method</p> <p>Birth control that lasts days, weeks, or months. Examples include: birth control pills, vaginal rings, skin patches, or contraceptive injections.</p>	د لنډې مودې هورموني میتود	پ امیندواري د مخنیوی لپاره لنډمهالي هورموني درمل
<p>Shoulder dystocia</p> <p>A condition that occurs when the one or both of a baby's shoulders get stuck when the baby is exiting the pelvis. Extra steps may be needed to deliver the baby.</p>	د اوږې ډیستوشی	د ولادت په وخت د ماشوم د اوږې بند پاتی کیدنه
<p>Speculum</p> <p>A medical tool used to hold open the walls of the vagina for examination of the vagina and cervix.</p>	سپیکولوم (د رحم دننه د کتلو وسیله/آله)	
<p>Spermicide</p> <p>Chemicals, including creams, gels, foams, that stop sperm from moving. Spermicide is inserted into the vagina before sex and is used as method of birth control.</p>	سپرم وژونکي	
<p>Still birth</p> <p>The death or loss of a baby after 20 weeks of pregnancy or during birth.</p>	د مړه ماشوم زېږول	
<p>Transvaginal ultrasound</p> <p>A type of imaging test to look at the uterus, ovaries, fallopian tubes, cervix, and pelvic area. A handheld probe will be gently placed inside the vagina. The ultrasound machine sends out sound waves that reflect off body structures to create a picture.</p>	ټرانس واژینال (د لمنی له لاري تلویزوني/التراساونډ) معاینه	

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<p>Trimesters</p> <p>A pregnancy is divided into three, three-month time periods.</p>	ترايمسترونه	
<p>Tubal ligation</p> <p>A form of permanent female birth control. Tubal ligation works by tying the fallopian tubes closed to prevent the passage of eggs from the ovaries to the uterus.</p>	د نفیرونو بندول	
<p>Umbilical cord</p> <p>A tube-like structure that connects the unborn baby to the placenta. The umbilical cord delivers nutrients and oxygen and removes waste products.</p>	د ماشوم نه/نوم	
<p>Unintended pregnancy</p> <p>A pregnancy that is unexpected or occurs without trying.</p>	ناغوښتل شوې امېندواري	
<p>Urethral catheter</p> <p>A tube used to drain urine from the bladder.</p>	د بولو د مجرا پایپ	
<p>Urinary tract infection</p> <p>An infection in any part of the urinary system including the kidneys, ureters, bladder, and urethra. Symptoms may include pain or burning during urination, cloudy or bad-smelling urine, feeling a need to urinate often or right away, pain in the back or lower abdomen, fever, and vomiting.</p>	د بولو د مجرا عفونت	
<p>Uterine contractions</p> <p>The tightening up of uterine muscles.</p>	د رحم تقلصونه	

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<p>Uterine prolapse</p> <p>A condition where the uterus move down from its normal position to press into or out of the vagina.</p>	د رحم پرولپس (د لمنی له لاری د رحم راوتل)	
<p>Uterus</p> <p>A muscular organ. During pregnancy, the uterus holds and nourishes the unborn baby.</p>	رحم	
<p>Vagina</p> <p>The internal passage leading from the cervix of the uterus to the opening of the body.</p>	مهبل	
<p>Vaginal discharge</p> <p>A clear or whitish fluid that comes out of the vagina. Discharge is normal, but changes in amount, thickness, color or smell could indicate an infection.</p>	د مهبل ترشحات	
<p>Vasectomy</p> <p>A form of permanent male birth control. A vasectomy works by cutting the tubes that carry sperm out of the testicles.</p>	واژکتومي (د سريانود نفيرونو بندول)	
<p>Viable</p> <p>Ability of the unborn baby to live under normal conditions outside the uterus.</p>	ژوندی پاتې کېدونکی حمل	
<p>Well-woman visit</p> <p>A yearly checkup with a healthcare provider that focuses on a woman's sexual, reproductive, and overall health. This may also be called an annual exam.</p>	د ښځی کلنی معاینه	

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<p>Withdrawal method</p> <p>The process of removing the penis from the vagina to ejaculate outside the vagina. This method is less effective than other options of birth control and also does not protect against sexually transmitted infections.</p>	احتياط	
<p>Yeast infection</p> <p>Yeast is a fungus that can cause infection in the vagina, vulva and other parts of the body. This fungal infection can cause itching, burning or irritation.</p>	د مهبل فنگسي عفونت	

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